

Group authorship: The connotations, characteristics, and progress of such a less popular authorship pattern

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Abstract

With the advent of the big science era, scientific collaboration has become broader and deeper, with a shift away from research produced by individual scientists toward team-based production. This has led to a greater diversity of authorship patterns, with group authorship emerging and developing as a particular form of collaboration. Group authorship refers to adding research groups to the author byline to balance the value and significance of individual authors and research groups. However, little attention has been given to this notable topic, and even the basic concept of "group authorship" is unclear. Therefore, based on the clarification of the concept of group authorship, this paper sorts out the reasons for its emergence as well as its development history and collaborative characteristics, further revealing the problems and challenges that still exist. Then we put forward corresponding recommendations from three aspects: authors, journals and publishers, and bibliographic databases, to deepen the related researchers' understanding of group authorship comprehensively.

Keywords: Group authorship; Individual author; Research group; Scientific collaboration

Introduction

The trend towards complexity, interdisciplinarity, and diversity in scientific research has raised a tremendous challenge for scholars to independently conduct complex research tasks. Nowadays, most scientific activities are performed in teams, with a corresponding increase in the average number of authors per paper. Several studies have documented that the dominance of multi-authored publications or team-based publications has increased over the years (Esparza & Yamada, 2007; Stokols et al., 2008; Wuchty et al., 2007). In response to the scientific phenomenon of an increasing number of authors participating in a paper, researchers have creatively attempted to add a research group that includes all authors on the author byline for authorship. This novel authorship pattern first emerged and evolved in clinical medicine, as studies in this field involve a significant number of large-scale, international, multicenter clinical trials and collaborations. The completion of such studies integrates the contributions of many researchers and requires the granting of authorship to recognize their contributions. At the same time, journals and publishers are increasingly receiving manuscripts with research groups on author byline. To accommodate this novelty, journals, and publishers accepted this authorship pattern and adapted it to their own circumstances. Since then, the authorship pattern has become more diverse, including single authorship and coauthorship, and group authorship. Regarding the definition, the group author is defined as follows:

Group author, also called corporate author or collaborative author, is an organization or institution that is credited with authorship of a source publication such as an article, a book, a proceeding, or another type of work, which will be listed as an author on the author byline (Editorials of JMIR, 2022; Web of Science, 2020).

However, little attention has been given to this specific authorship pattern, and even the basic concept of "group author" is ambiguous. To date, there has been little research on group authorship, and the few articles that have been published have focused simply on two issues:

one is the discussion of the changes in group authorship by the editorial material of journals in the medical field, of which the JAMA editorials have more discussion on this (Flanagin et al., 2002; Glass, 1992); and the other is the discussion of the potential problems of group authorship, mainly including the problems with indexing and citation (Dickersin et al., 2002; Mackinnon & Clarke, 2002).

Therefore, it can be found that so far, limited related studies have been focused on group authorship, and the knowledge points expressed are too loose, lacking a systematic review and combing. In addition, group authorship emerged in the last century, and the related literature was mainly published in the late 20th century or early 21st century, with a "hiatus" of nearly two decades in the study of group authorship. Based on this, this paper first introduces the reasons for the emergence of group authorship, then sorts out its development history and collaboration characteristics, further reveals the problems and challenges that still exist, and puts forward corresponding recommendations in the end, aiming to help scholars understand this authorship pattern comprehensively.

Connotations of group author

The most important feature of a group author, and the one that distinguishes it from general authorship, is the addition of the research group's name on the author byline to indicate authorship. In addition to this, the group author has the same responsibilities and rights as a single author and coauthor, such as disclosing potential conflicts of interest, ensuring the manuscript is prepared for review, holding full copyright and self-archiving rights, deciding which type of publishing to pursue, and so on.

At present, the number of articles involving a large number of researchers working under a research group has been increasing in the sciences, particularly in medical science or life sciences (Council of Science Editors, 2022). Such articles are known as collaborative, corporate, collective, or group-author articles. Group-author articles involve the following parties, summarized in Table 1. Among these, the relationship between individual authors and the research group is worth mentioning. Generally, individual authors refer to those who take responsibility for authorship, and he/she may or may not be a member of the research group. Further, the research group members who take responsibility for authorship are the authors of this article, so these members are also part of the individual authors.

Table 1. The following parties involved in group-author articles

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Subdivision</i>	<i>Description</i>
Individual authors	• Byline authors	Listed on author byline and take responsibility for authorship
	• Non-byline authors	Not listed on author byline but take responsibility for authorship
Research group	• Research group's name	The name of the organization or institution, or research team
	• Author group members (be included in individual authors)	Members of the group who take responsibility for authorship (may or may not be listed on the author byline)

- Non-author group members Members of the group who do not take responsibility for authorship but have contributed to the article

The formats of the author byline may include the name of a research group or consortium in several ways, such as in combination with individual authors or alone on the author byline. However, a standard format is often lacking, which can easily lead to difficulty in the discrimination of such articles in author contribution and has resulted in citation errors and miscalculated citation statistics (Dickersin et al., 2002). Based on this, the Council of Science Editors (CSE) proposed recommendations to ensure that group-author articles can be accurately cited, and that all elements of group-author articles can be retrieved, such as the name of the research group and individual authors. The CSE recommendations are currently the most relevant and authoritative descriptions for group-author articles, which were drafted in 2003, discussed and revised by staff at JAMA, PLOS Medicine, NEJM, PNAS, CMAJ, Science, US-NLM, and HighWire Press.

The common formats on the author byline are summarized in Figure 1 and Table 2 and described below.

Figure 1. The common formats on author byline

Individual authors "for" a research group

The author byline contains the names of individual authors and the name of the research group, connected by "for". While some journals prefer to use ";" or "on behalf of" instead of "for". Individuals who meet authorship criteria are listed on the author byline, followed by the name of the research group. The individual authors are writing on behalf of or representing the research group, designated as "for" the research group, in which case the nonbyline members of the research group do not meet authorship criteria and are not authors but may be listed as collaborators in somewhere else in the article (for example, in the "Acknowledgment" section). In addition, although not all authors may be listed on the author byline (especially when the number of authors is huge and the space is insufficient), all authors who meet the authorship criteria, as well as the research group name, will be recorded and retrieved in databases.

Individual authors "and" a research group

The author byline contains the names of individual authors and the name of the research group, connected by "and". While some journals prefer to use ";" instead of "and". Individuals who meet authorship criteria are listed on the author byline of the article, followed by the research group's name. All research group members are authors and meet the full criteria and requirements for authorship. The use of the connector "and" indicates that there are other

individual authors who are not named on the byline (called nonbyline author) but are members of the research group and are listed somewhere else in the article, usually in the "Acknowledgment" section or in the Appendix section at the end of the article. In addition, although not all authors may be listed on the author byline (especially when the number of authors is huge and the space is insufficient), all authors who meet the authorship criteria, as well as the research group name, will be recorded and retrieved in databases.

Research group

Some authors and research groups might prefer that only the group name appears on the author byline without individual authors' names to emphasize the scientific research's collaborative nature. In this case, no individual authors are listed on the author byline, and all members of the research group are authors, which will be listed in the "Acknowledgments" or "Appendix" section at the end of the article. This format requires clear justification that all research group members meet the full authorship criteria and requirements. However, a disadvantage of this format is that the individual authors who are responsible for the article can only be found by reading the full text, which causes inconveniences to readers as well as troubles with retrieval, collection, and statistics. In addition, all authors in the research group as well as the research group name will be recorded and retrieved in databases.

*Research group**

The author byline contains the name of the research group but no named individual authors. However, in contrast with example (3), not all members of the research group are authors, and use of asterisk behind the group name. The asterisk on the author byline also appears somewhere else in the article to introduce the research group and the members of the group who take responsibility for the article (Flanagin et al., 2002). In databases, the authors in the research group who meet the authorship criteria, as well as the research group name, will be recorded and retrieved.

Subgroup "for" the research group

The author byline includes the subgroup name and the research group name. The members of the subgroup (e.g., the "writing committee" of the research group) are all part of the research group, and all meet the authorship criteria. The specific authorship information can be disclosed in the "Acknowledgments" section at the end of the article. In databases, all authors of the subgroup, as well as the subgroup name and research group name, will be recorded and retrieved.

Although there are many formats for author byline, the most commonly used is combining individual authors with the research group, which highlights the primary authors of the article and also considers the research group. However, the format of including only the group name on the author byline does not distinguish those who qualify for authorship from those who do not, so it is rarely used.

Table 2. Links and differences in common formats on author byline

<i>Common formats on author byline</i>	<i>Who are the authors?</i>	<i>Are all members of the research group authors?</i>	<i>What author information can be retrieved from databases?</i>
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Individual Authors "for" a Research Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual Authors • Members of the research group who meet the authorship criteria 	No	Authors, the name of the research group
Individual Authors "and" a Research Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual Authors • All members of the research group 	Yes	Authors, the name of the research group
Research Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All members of the research group 	Yes	Authors, the name of the research group
Research Group*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Members of the research group who meet the authorship criteria 	No	Authors, the name of the research group
Subgroup "for" a Research Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All members of the subgroup 	No, but all members of the subgroup are authors	Authors, the name of the subgroup, and the research group

Emergence and early exploration of group authorship

Reasons for the emergence of group authorship

Group authorship has been recognized since at least 1841 (Dickersin et al., 2002), but it had not become popular at that time. Until the 1980s, large, international, multicenter clinical trials have become increasing prevalence, requiring the participation, collaboration, and dedication of many authors, raising the question of how to share the credit among many authors, thus giving group authorship to the popular (Weeks et al., 2004). Proponents of group author point out that it is useful in studies where credit should be shared among many authors because this format offers hope for the emergence of a new social-medical ethic in which the focus is shifted from the individuals to groups and where wholes are more highly valued than individuals, especially in large multicenter trials in clinical medicine or biomedicine (Meinert, 1993). However, Kassirer and Angell argue that when many authors appear in the long list of a research group, it is difficult to distinguish the actual contribution of each author, and it is not clear who can be truly responsible for the article, which tends to blur the distinction between authors and those who merely warrant acknowledgment (Kassirer & Angell, 1991). Thus, in general, the emergence and development of group authorship have been accompanied by both supportive and opposing voices. In addition to the reason mentioned above, the emergence of the group author is also stimulated by the following several factors.

One of the most important factors is the increased complexity of studies and the increase in multicenter research collaborations. The joint research work of large-scale projects requires the collaboration of talents from multi-country, multi-institution, or multi-discipline. In the past decade, traditional single investigator-initiated research projects have been transformed into teams of co-investigators and consultants (Okamoto & Hlth, 2015). Scientific research is conducted as networks, consortia, and large research centers are funded as transdisciplinary,

team-based enterprises to tackle complex scientific questions. This shift makes scientific research increasingly require the power of teamwork. Bacharach and Tollefsen (2010) argued that some collaboratively produced works are completed by a group rather than any individual. Indeed, when a group is an author like this, it has advantages that no individual member of the group possesses (Corsa, 2020), such as integrating resources, conquering major projects, achieving major innovations, etc.

From a journal perspective, there is limited space for the author's byline on the title page, including the title and abstract (Glass, 1992; Weeks et al., 2004). If an article has a large number of authors (e.g., more than 50 or 100), there is no space on the title page to accommodate all of them. In these cases, other options may need to be considered, such as listing the group name only on the author byline and listing the individual authors who take responsibility for the article in the acknowledgments section or the appendices, along with their affiliations, contributions, and conflicts of interest disclosures (Fontanarosa et al., 2017). Some studies have shown that group author has been used more commonly if journals had a restriction on the maximum number of authors on the byline (Weeks et al., 2004) (e.g., the Scandinavian Journal of Surgery allows a maximum of eight authors (Scandinavian Journal of Surgery, 2022)), and the strong form restriction is much more effective than weak form restriction. The former is a clear statement that the maximum number of authors cannot be exceeded, while the latter requires the submission of a statement when the maximum number of authors is exceeded. (Weeks et al., 2004).

From special requirements, some institutions or databases clearly state that using their data for scientific research or teaching requires the signing of the "Data use agreement" and, if necessary, adding the group name (i.e., the organization or database) on the author byline to indicate that the research is supported by the institution or database (Huang, 2018). For example, Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) is a collaborative project of over 30 institutions from Canada and the United States. The researchers in this project have built their collected and validated data on Alzheimer's disease into the ADNI database, which can be downloaded in different formats by users worldwide. According to the ADNI database requirements, if ADNI data is used in the body of a published article, the group author (i.e., "for the ADNI") needs to be added to the author byline, at the same time, explicitly explaining in the methods section of the article that the data is from ADNI (Alzheimer's, 2016).

In terms of well-known large research institutions or companies are often better known than the names of individual authors, so signaling a group name on the author byline is more likely to increase the impact of the research (Flanagin et al., 2002). For example, the group/team "ATLAS Collaboration", comprising more than 2,000 scientists in 165 working groups located around the world, has made significant contributions to physics. Hence, researchers in physics or related fields may open the article to see what further cutting-edge research the group/team has done when the article is bylined with the "ATLAS Collaboration". On the contrary, if the article is bylined with Henderson, RCW, or Barton, AE, etc., who are members of the "ATLAS Collaboration", it may not attract more reading or citations.

In addition, if a study receives leadership and funding from an institution/corporation, uses the research foundation of the institution/corporation to conduct a study, or employs the members of the institution/corporation to be experimentees, these cases all may be required to add group author (i.e., the institution or corporation) on the author byline. Additionally, group author may also be used for documents such as general building development plans or summaries of an institution, corporation, school, or administrative unit, but this is not the main reason.

Early exploration of group authorship

The early development characteristics of group authorship can be presented at the level of authors, journals and publishers, and bibliographic databases.

For authors: For a long time after its emergence, group author has been popular mainly in the medical field, and a trend has developed in that field. While in other fields, especially in the humanities and social sciences, group author has not been well developed, utilized, and popularized, and this has happened not only in the past but also in the present. As a result, searching for group author or group-author articles is difficult for most users or scholars, whether searching in journals and publishers or in bibliographic databases, since they have little knowledge or recognition of group authors and are probably unaware of indexing rules (Dickersin et al., 2002).

For journals and publishers: Due to the development of multicenter clinical trials, group authorship is very popular in medical journals, which have made changes to address the increase in group-author articles. For example, the Journal of the American Medical Association (JAMA) has supported group authorship. Considering the role of multicenter collaborative groups in addressing important questions and the necessity for clear and accountable authorship responsibility, JAMA has permitted authorship to be attributed to a research group, as long as all members of the research group meet the full criteria and requirements for authorship (Glass, 1992; International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), 2022). In addition, JAMA recommended using a research group on the author byline and listing individual names at the end of the article when there are a large number of authors (e.g., >50) (JAMA, 2022). Also, a study has proved that the prevalence of group authorship in four medical journals such as the Annals of Internal Medicine, Archives of Internal Medicine, JAMA, and the New England Journal of Medicine (NEJM), has far exceeded that of single authorship and coauthorship (Weeks et al., 2004).

However, group-author articles may have the problems of ambiguous authorship and lengthy acknowledgments. Therefore, to truly reflect the meaning of authorship and the value of an acknowledgment, the NEJM made a significant change in 1991 that authorship attributed only to a research group will not be acceptable, but instead, at least one individual name must accompany the group name. In addition, given the large number of research group members, NEJM noted that if the acknowledgments exceed the length of a journal column, the journal will no longer display this separately but will instead deposit them with the National Auxiliary Publications Service (Kassirer & Angell, 1991).

In general, major journals in the medical field have taken the lead in responding to the group author phenomenon. However, the citation format of group-author articles recommended by different journals is inconsistent, which may lead to citation errors and miscalculations of citation statistics (Dickersin et al., 2002).

For bibliographic databases: It was not until the 21st century that major bibliographic databases developed separate group-author retrieval fields and related indexing services intending to accommodate the development of group authors. For example, prior to 2001, there was no separate group author field in the MEDLINE database, but group names could be included as an additional field to the title for searching (Dickersin et al., 2002). In 2001, MEDLINE introduced a new separate group author field to identify the group authorship of articles (National Library of Medicine, 2018). In addition, in 2005, the latest version of the Web of Science (WoS) database added several new search paths, search interfaces, and linking

features, with group author appearing as a newly added search path for finding literature published by institutions or research groups (Du & Chen, 2005). Subsequently, WoS recorded and updated group authorship data for the years after 1995, while group author data for 1995 and earlier were incomplete (Wan, 2014). It can be observed that some important bibliographic databases were relatively late in developing the group-author field, which invisibly weakened the impact of earlier group-author articles. Indeed, some databases do not recognize group-author names on the author byline implies a lesser status of these articles (Dickersin et al., 2002).

Overall, in the early stage of group authorship development, journals, publishers, and bibliographic databases have taken steps to deal with the phenomenon of research groups appearing on author byline, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Early development characteristics of group authorship

<i>Main dimensions</i>	<i>Early development characteristics</i>
Authors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most authors do not understand the group authorship pattern; • Most authors do not know the indexing rules for retrieving group-author articles;
Journals and publishers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group authorship is popular in medical journals; • The citation format or signature requirements for group-author articles recommended by different journals are inconsistent;
Bibliographic databases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major bibliographic databases are relatively late in the development of separate group-author retrieval fields and related indexing services intending.

Collaboration characteristics of group-author articles

After entering the 21st century, well-known databases have developed group-author fields and recorded group-author data, and since then, researchers have been able to analyze group-author data on a large scale. Therefore, we take 2000 as the starting year to analyze the development of group authors in the two decades from 2000 to 2019. Group author data were obtained from WoS, the world's largest and most prestigious citation database.

When using WoS to retrieve group author data, users can enter the names of group authors in the "Group Author" field or use the "Group Author Index" to help locate the primary group author to add to users' queries. It is worth noting that either approach should consider the different forms of names, using acronyms and truncations to create queries. For example, to find papers by the group author of "Women's Interagency HIV Study", users can enter "women* interag* HIV*" or "WIHS*" in the group author field to retrieve or enter "W" in the group author index to help target the "Women's Interagency HIV Study". What's more, in the Advanced Search, the field identifier for the group author is "GP". (But, unlike in WoS, in PubMed or MEDLINE, the group author can be retrieved by the "Corporate Author" field, not the "Group Author" field, and the field identifier in Advanced Search for group author is "CN", not "GP".)

According to the above search rules, we collected the group-author articles published during 2000-2019 from the core collection of WoS (limited to SCIE, SSCI, and A&HCI) by the

following data retrieval: GP = (A* OR B* OR C* OR D* OR E* OR F* OR G* OR H* OR I* OR J* OR K* OR L* OR M* OR N* OR O* OR P* OR Q* OR R* OR S* OR T* OR U* OR V* OR W* OR X* OR Y* OR Z* OR 0* OR 1* OR 2* OR 3* OR 4* OR 5* OR 6* OR 7* OR 8* OR 9*), and finally resulting in a total of 177,331 articles (Retrieval date is June 8, 2020).

Development trend

The development and prevalence of group authorship can be reflected in the evolution of the number of group-author articles and their share of total WoS articles. Then, to make the analysis comparable, we searched for articles in the three major indexes in WoS from 2000 to 2019. The result is shown in Figure 2. The number of group-author articles has been steadily increasing, more than doubling during that period. However, in the context of an increasing total volume of articles year after year, the proportion of group-author articles in total articles has been meager and almost always fluctuates around 0.7%, indicating that the overall prevalence of group authorship remains low.

Figure 2. Trends in the number and share of group-author articles over time

In addition, Table 4 lists the top 10 research groups with the highest number of published group-author articles. Of these, except for ADNI, which is dedicated to disease research, the remaining nine research groups are in the field of physics, dedicated to the research, discovery, and maintenance of collider detectors, a large physical device. Because the data generated by collider detectors are so large and need to be supported by more than 130 supercomputers distributed around the world, research in this field often requires a superabundance of people working together across countries, regions, and centers. For example, the "CMS Collaboration" includes approximately 4,300 scientists, engineers, and technicians from 42 countries and 190 institutions. Participants work in hundreds of subteams organized into two major categories: physics and service. An essential task of "CMS Collaboration" is to observe the Higgs boson, which is important to the fundamental understanding of the universe because it helps to explain why matter has mass (National Research Council, 2015). Correspondingly, research to date has shown that the particle physics field has a unique organizational structure (Shrum et al., 2007)

and collaborative culture (Traweek & Kernan, 1990) and that these inherent features are strongly associated with the use of group authorship.

Table 4. Top 10 research groups with the highest number of group-author articles

<i>Research groups</i>	<i>No. of group-author articles</i>	<i>Research groups</i>	<i>No. of group-author articles</i>
CMS Collaboration	1316	PHENIX Collaboration	571
ATLAS Collaboration	1212	ADNI	572
ASDEX Upgrade Team	968	LHCb Collaboration	569
STAR Collaboration	753	CDF Collaboration	537
ALICE Collaboration	692	BABAR Collaboration	533

Collaboration scale

From the above reasons for group author, we understand that group author is mostly accompanied by labels such as complex studies, large collaborations, and multicenter trials, and thus group-author articles may have a larger scale of collaboration compared to other articles. Hence, to test the validity of our hypothesis, we compared the number of authors in group-author articles and other multi-author articles.

Figure 3 shows that the collaboration scale in group-author articles presents a skewed distribution, with most having only a few authors and a few having a large number of authors (A collaboration scale of 0 means that the article is signed only by the name of the research group and does not list any individual authors). This distribution is consistent with the multi-author report published by Institute for Scientific Information (ISI) in 2020 (Institute for Scientific Information, 2020). The collaboration scale of group-author articles was mainly concentrated between 1 and 15 authors. Among them, the collaboration scale of six authors published the largest number of group-author articles, followed by seven, eight, five, ten, and nine authors, all of whom published more than 10,000 group-author articles. While the most common number of authors on an article in WoS is three (Institute for Scientific Information, 2020), this is significantly lower than that in group-author articles. Besides, group-author articles with a collaboration scale of more than ten authors accounted for 42%, far exceeding 5% in general articles in WoS (Institute for Scientific Information, 2020). Hence, the comparison shows that in group-author articles, both the most common number of authors and the proportion of articles with more than 10 authors are higher than in general articles, implying that the collaboration scale in group-author articles is often larger than that in general articles.

Figure 3. Distribution of the number of authors in group-author articles

The major challenges faced by scientific research increasingly require large teams to tackle them, and with that comes the need for collaboration on equipment, data, and talent. As a result, the collaboration scale required to complete a major study may be increased. Prior to 2000, the collaboration scale in an article rarely exceeded 500 authors. In 2003, the 1,000 caps were broken with a group-author article of 1,307 authors (Abbateo et al., 2003). "Hyper-authorship" (Cronin, 2001) seems to be flourishing, and the current record holder is an article published by "ATLAS Collaboration" in 2022 on the use of the LHC to study Bose-Einstein correlations between particles, with 8778 authors (ATLAS Collaboration & Newman, 2022). Further, to understand the evolutionary trend of the collaboration scale of group-author articles, we counted the most common collaboration scale and the median and maximum of each year, and the results are shown in Figure 4. It can be observed that the collaboration scale of group-author articles is increasing year by year, indicating the growing need for collaboration in scientific research.

Figure 4. The evolution of collaboration scale in group-author articles

Country collaboration pattern

The problems faced by the group author are often more complex, and the data collection and processing processes are often more diverse, resulting in a higher demand for international talent, multi-country data, and transnational equipment. Correspondingly, by extension of the collaboration scale, the likelihood of the phenomenon of transnational collaboration in group-author articles may be higher than that in other articles. To verify this point, we first split the national collaboration pattern into three types: National collaboration (NAC), Bilateral international collaboration (BIC), and Multilateral international collaboration (MIC). NAC refers to the collaboration of authors from the same country, BIC refers to the collaboration of authors from two different countries, and MIC refers to the collaboration of authors from more than two countries (Li & Li, 2015).

As shown in Figure 5, the percentage of group-author articles completed by authors from the same country (NAC), two different countries (BIC), and more than two countries (MIC) are 57.50%, 15.37%, and 27.13%, respectively. Furthermore, 86.57% of group-author articles have authors from five or fewer countries, which is less than that of the 99% of articles across the Web of Science (Institute for Scientific Information, 2020). Hence, the characteristic of international collaboration in group-author articles is more obvious than that in general articles.

Figure 5. Country collaboration pattern in group-author articles

Although NAC is the most frequent country collaboration pattern for both group-author articles and multi-author articles, the proportion of NAC in group-author articles is clearly on the decline over time (70.29%—63.35%—56.02%—49.32%), as Figure 6 shows. On the contrary, with the popularity of international collaboration, BIC and MIC are mounting up quickly. Temporally, international collaboration has occurred mainly in the last ten years, especially in the last five years, which indicates that the country collaboration patterns of group-author articles significantly evolved from NAC to BIC and MIC, and the characteristics of "international collaboration" and "multi-country authorship" in research are more and more obvious in group-author articles.

Figure 6. The evolution of country collaboration patterns

Remaining challenges of group authorship

After years of development, group authorship has gained some momentum and scale, but it still has not gained enough popularity and recognition. In the process of the development of group authorship, there are still many challenges that exist, which can be summarized as the problems of identifying, indexing, and citation in group-author articles, as well as the problems of ambiguous authorship, distribution of author contributions, and maintenance of author list in group-author articles, as shown below.

Different journals and publishers, as well as bibliographic databases, have inconsistent standard formats for group-author articles, which caused much trouble. Significantly, the absence of a standard format for the citation of group-author articles leads to citation errors and miscalculated citation statistics. For example, the authors have cited the article "Rising rural body-mass index is the main driver of the global obesity epidemic in adults" (Bixby et al., 2019) published in *Nature* in 2019 by listing the group author of "NCD Risk Factor Collaboration" or by listing the first author (i.e., Bixby, Honor, et al.). Some databases erroneously identified these types of citations as two different articles and thus reported an undercount of total citations to this article. This may result in the risk of authors not receiving the credit they deserve (Andersen et al., 2020) and lead to misrepresentation of journal impact.

In addition to the absence of a standard format for citation, the more original problem is that not all of the earlier group-author articles are well-updated. As pointed out in existing studies, bibliographic databases are not always optimized for group authorship, especially for articles prior to the 21st century (Dickersin et al., 2002; Flanagan et al., 2002). As a result, there may still be questions about "whether research groups can be retrieved as authors" and "whether authorship information for group-author articles is comprehensive" in earlier group-authored articles. Thus, identifying, indexing, and citation become dilemmas in group-author articles (Dickersin et al., 2002; Mackinnon & Clarke, 2002).

Group authorship may be accompanied by a huge number of authors, such as "ATLAS Collaboration" or "CMS Collaboration" that often publish articles with large collaborations of

several thousand authors, which is a common situation in the field of particle physics. But two questions tend to arise, who is the real author, and how to distribute the author's contributions?

For example, the article published by "ATLAS Collaboration" in 2022 includes 8778 authors, which, in addition to physicists, include technicians, engineers, and programmers at all kinds of levels. In fact, no more than a handful of the "authors" listed on the record-breaking paper have even read the article, never mind written any of it (Coles, 2015). Then this has led to a lot of discussion about how to deal with these people who may not be "authors" in the literal sense but who do contribute to the research indeed. Some considered that the final act of analysis, interpretation, and writing is one of the easier ones to complete an article and that those who contribute to the project initiation, system operation, equipment development, process maintenance, etc., cannot be ignored even more, and should also be given authorship of such people as well (Meinert, 1993). On the contrary, opponents argued that such people are too remote from the article or had too limited a role in exercising the responsibility that authorship implied (Kassirer & Angell, 1991) and are instead more suitable as collaborators or mentioned in the acknowledgments (Fontanarosa et al., 2017). To this day, this issue and the related discussions still exist.

This leads to the second question of how to distribute the credits or contributions of authors. Since so many people are involved in the research, it is difficult to distinguish who contributed the most. As a result, a convention has developed in some fields (e.g., particle physics) that the authors of research groups are always listed in alphabetical order rather than in contributions (Dickersin et al., 2002), with no clear indication of their contributions, ignoring the distribution of contributions of researchers and not reflecting the authenticity of scientific work.

Also, research groups are subject to change, such as the addition of new members, changes in members' workplaces, or the death of a member, which are particularly evident in longer-term studies. Thus, a change in group membership risks applying responsibility to a new research group member who was not involved in the study that the research group had authored (Andersen et al., 2020). In addition, due to the long research period, the workplace of hundreds of people may have changed by the time the research is finally completed, making it too inefficient for the editorial team to check this authorship information one by one (Kassirer and Angell). Even more, an article may have a deceased author at the time of publication. For example, an article announcing the ATLAS team's observation of the Higgs particle in 2012 was published, with 21 of the 2,932 authors listed as deceased (Aad et al., 2012). All of the above may lead to problems of ambiguous responsibility ownership and also increase the difficulty of author list maintenance.

Furthermore, scientists often use data from relevant databases for experimental research but often have problems with improper citation formatting of databases, and failure to follow the "Data use agreement" clearly specified by the database, such as not adding the group author on the author byline, and so on. Taking the ADNI database as an example, nearly half of the articles published in the WoS do not comply with the "Data use agreement" and are not signed and acknowledged as required (Huang, 2018). On the one hand, many people do not recognize the importance of the "Data use agreement" and think that a brief mention of the database is sufficient, or simply do not notice the website's requirements for data usage. On the other hand, editors or journal executives do not generally accept group authors and are not aware of the agreement and formats that need to be followed when citing data from databases.

In general, group author has tended to create confusion as to who should be responsible and credited in scientific articles. Therefore, if one chooses to publish with a group author, a good reason should be given, as a group author may be associated with considerable challenges.

Conclusion and discussion

Scientific collaboration has been identified as a promising approach to hasten scientific progress to address complex and multifactorial social problems (Gibert et al., 2017; Potter et al., 2020). This has been shown in the literature, with the "nearly universal rise since 1975 in the frequency of collaborations among authors representing different disciplines and located at different universities" (Jones et al., 2008). Among this trend, "grouping" authors from diverse disciplines, institutions, or even countries have become increasingly prevalent, which involves some indication of group participation and responsibility, reflecting the collaborative nature, multidisciplinary teamwork, and complexity of scientific research (Flanagin et al., 2002). Clearly, scientific collaboration has a critically important role in promoting the emergence of group authorship. Indeed, compared with multi-author articles, group-author articles generally have a larger collaboration scale and broader international collaboration.

In the last two decades, the number of group-author articles has been increasing, with solid growth in recent years. However, group authorship still faces some difficulties and challenges after decades or even centuries of development, such as the problems of identifying, indexing, and citation, partly because of the lack of comprehensive and timely updating and optimization, and partly because of the absence of a standard format for citation of group-author articles. In addition, group-author articles may involve hundreds or even thousands of authors and in this case, may face the problem of ambiguous authorship and ambiguous contributions. At the same time, it is too inefficient for the editorial team to check this massive authorship information one by one, making it more difficult to maintain the author list, and too many acknowledgments are not a good use of journal space. An interesting issue is that if a group-author article involves too many authors, say several thousand, then the author list may include numerous experts in this field, so who will do the peer review? Meanwhile, research groups are subject to change, such as the addition of new members, changes in members' workplaces, or the death of a member, which may result in unclear attribution of responsibility and difficulties in maintaining the author list.

Based on the abovementioned issues, we put forward relevant recommendations at the level of authors, journals and publishers, and bibliographic databases for the development of group authorship. Firstly, authors need to understand group authorship fully and be clear about the meaning, relationship, and significance between the various identities. Authors choosing group authorship must be aware of the possible risks, such as indexing, citation, etc. After that, the authorship is given to those who fulfill the authorship criteria. In the order of authorship, a clear division of labor is recommended, just like the cast of a movie, to determine their respective contributions to avoid ambiguous authorship and ambiguous contributions. Secondly, journals and publishers should make efforts to standardize group-author articles by, for example, requiring authors to identify the names of individual authors and research groups, coding or formatting the names, indicating a suggested citation style in which to display the "research groups", and helping authors to use the correct symbols connecting individual authors and research groups. In addition, for the problems of ambiguous authorship and lengthy acknowledgments, it is recommended that journals and publishers develop corresponding guidelines for authorship and acknowledgments, such as setting an upper limit on the authors' number and the length of acknowledgments. Finally, the bibliographic database should proactively develop the retrieval field of group authors with no character limits to ensure that

users can retrieve all authors by individual authors as well as by research groups. Then, update the information on group-author articles as soon as possible to achieve standardized development of group authorship. Additionally, the bibliographic databases lack an evaluation module on the impact of research groups, and consideration could be given to adding relevant indicators or visual graphs to reflect the contribution of research groups to scientific research.

Our work has important theoretical value for understanding the less popular authorship pattern of group authorship. In conclusion, group authorship is a good choice for some fields because it highlights both the main authors and the research groups that contributed to the article. However, like all policies, these are subject to periodic reevaluation and modification as needed. The criteria for evaluating a new collaboration form depends on whether such a pattern contributes to productivity and impact. Therefore, further observation remains on whether the group author becomes a mainstream authorship form. Although group author is not very popular now and there are still some problems, they can be gradually improved in the future, and we should treat it with an open and developing perspective.

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